

ASSESSING THE READING COMPREHENSION OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS USING THE PHILIPPINE INFORMAL READING INVENTORY (PHIL-IRI)

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Abstract

This study assesses the reading comprehension of Grade 7 students using the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) through a mixed-method research design that combines quantitative and qualitative approaches. Quantitative data, analyzed via mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage distribution, evaluated students' oral reading performance, while qualitative data underwent thematic analysis to identify response patterns and deepen understanding of students' reading abilities based on their experiences. Findings revealed varied comprehension levels, with many students struggling particularly with inferential questions and vocabulary recognition. Thematic analysis highlighted recurring challenges such as limited exposure to reading materials, lack of interest in reading, and insufficient reading support at home. In response, the study recommends targeted interventions including vocabulary enrichment, reading motivation programs, and guided reading sessions to enhance the reading comprehension skills of Grade 7 learners.

Keywords: *assessment, grade 7, phil-iri, reading comprehension, reading proficiency*

Introduction

Reading comprehension is one of the most important skills for accomplishing the primary goals of the reading process. It is the foundation of successful learning in a variety of topic areas and entails comprehending, analyzing, and evaluating textual texts. Reading comprehension, the ability to understand what is written, is a fundamental skill crucial for academic success and lifelong learning (Espia, E., & Cortezano, G. 2023). Reading skill can promote lifelong education and training (Merga & Roni, 2018)

Moreover, reading is one of the most essential abilities a pupil should develop (Peng & Kievit, 2020). The ability of the child to read or even master how to read will give them a sense of satisfaction and accomplishment, which will build their self-esteem. It contributes to everyone's academic performance (Erp, 2021). In this regard, reading comprehension is the ability to read

without emphasizing pronunciation or speed reading—instead, it emphasizes understanding the text (Smith et al., 2021).

However, despite its importance, reading is also regarded as a challenging skill, so things don't always go as planned. Reading is a challenging process to learn and equally challenging to teach (Janette, 2007). In addition, reading is an activity undertaken by someone to gather information about something which involves three essential elements: the reader, the text, and the process of comprehending the text (Siregar, 2018).

In 2021 literacy results for the National Assessment Program Literacy and Numeracy (NAPLAN), which all Australian students sit in Years 3, 5, 7 and 9, the Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority (Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority, 2021) noted that the average trend in reading and spelling is upward, with writing levelling out

from the decline of previous years. Preliminary research suggests that students already experiencing reading difficulties may be further impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic and, while it has been suggested that the impact of the pandemic on Australian students is limited (Gore, J., Fray, L., Miller, A., Harris, J., & Taggart, W. (2021); Productivity Commission. (2022), recent changes in the approach to the public health crisis mean that this is yet to be fully understood.

In 2019, the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metric [SEA-PLM] reported that a percentage of Filipino fifth graders performance exhibited least proficiency in three learning areas: mathematics, writing and reading (Bernardo et al., 2022).

The Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM) 2019 assessment, conducted by UNICEF and the Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization (SEAMEO), evaluated the learning outcomes of Grade 5 students across six Southeast Asian countries: Cambodia, Lao PDR, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, and Vietnam. The assessment measured proficiencies in reading, writing, and mathematics. The grade five learners' performance was assessed from chosen schools in six countries of Southeast Asia. It was evident in the data that Philippines is the second-least performer in reading with 10 percent, followed by Laos with a performance of only 2 percent (UNICEF and SEAMEO, 2020). Moreover, they found out that the reading difficulties of grade five pupils were particularly manifested on level of word recognition and reading comprehension (Rivera and Aggabao 2020).

Additionally, the pressing concern regarding reading comprehension among

Furthermore, it was found that most pupils in one of the schools in Northern Mindanao are categorized as frustrated readers, and a significant number fall under

pupils in Philippine education is evident in the PISA program. The Philippines joined the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development's (OECD) (2023) PISA program as part of the quality primary education reform strategy and a move toward internationalizing Philippine primary education. The Philippines has participated in the initiative above for the past two years. The Philippines first took part in 2018, ranking 78th in math and science and last in reading comprehension, with pupils scoring 340 points, the lowest among all participating countries. In contrast, the Philippines ranked 79th in science, 76th in math, 76th in reading, and 77th in the 2022 PISA results. While there may be slight improvements in the Philippines' PISA results and standing, this still demonstrates that Filipino pupils continue to lack skills in complex problem-solving, critical thinking, and effective communication, particularly in reading, when compared to other countries, preventing schools from fulfilling their goal of producing excellent and well-informed citizens. Not all Filipino pupils have a desirable reading comprehension level. Some needed help extracting the meaning from the written material and going beyond the text (Fernandez & Arriola, 2022).

In the Philippines, the literacy rate was reported at 96% in 2019 (World Population Review, 2024). However, reading comprehension remained a significant concern. According to the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), the Philippines ranked 76th out of 81 participating countries in reading comprehension (Servallos, 2023). This was not a new trend; in the 2018 PISA, the country had ranked the lowest among 79 nations, indicating a persistent challenge in improving reading skills among Filipino students.

the non-readers category (Ong et al., 2021). In some schools in the Division of El Salvador City, Misamis Oriental, the pupils' reading

performance in English is alarming (Sanoria & Oco, 2023).

Data from the Department of Education (DepEd) indicates that a significant percentage of Filipino students perform poorly in reading comprehension assessments (Villanueva, 2022, Tortola 2021). This deficiency can have a domino effect, impacting students' overall academic achievement and potentially limiting their career prospects (Hemmings, B., Kay, R., & Sharp, J. 2019).

Reading is extremely helpful since it exposes one to a wide range of perspectives, cultures, and ideas and expands one's knowledge. It also enhances understanding and critical thinking skills, which facilitate information processing, problem-solving and well-informed decision-making. Reading also fosters creativity and communication, which enables people to effectively express themselves and consider an array of choices. The ability to read is important to the learning of children along with the development of their skills in literacy and dynamic society involvement (DepEd, 2019). Hence, having the skill in reading is considered as a foothold for all academic learnings. In the DepEd Memorandum No. 173, series of 2019, it is emphasized that "the ability to read is fundamental to children's learning, including their development of broader literacy skills, and to their future successful participation in society." (Department of Education (DepEd). (2019). Bawat Bata Bumabasa Initiative (DepEd Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019). Department of Education, Philippines.)

The government and various educational stakeholders have implemented various interventions to improve reading comprehension skills, such as the Enhanced Basic Education Program (K to 12) curriculum with its focus on reading comprehension strategies (Hu, 2023).

The Department of Education (DepEd) developed the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) as an assessment tool to measure Filipino learners' reading proficiency. It evaluates a learner's ability in word recognition, fluency, and comprehension in both Filipino and English. The goal is to determine their reading level—whether independent, instructional, or frustrated. The Department of Education (DepEd) mandates the use of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) in schools to assess students' reading abilities. This initiative highlights the importance of strategically planning and implementing literacy improvement efforts, as emphasized by Abril et al. (2022).

DepEd Memorandum No. 266, s. 2010 – Administration of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI): This memorandum highlights the significance of creating reading level profiles for students in public elementary schools. It requires the use of the Phil-IRI to evaluate reading speed and understanding, which will guide specific interventions aimed at enhancing reading abilities. The usage of PHIL-IRI is commonly used in the Philippines in order to look at the reading efficiency of students because of DEPED's mandate (Abocejo et al., 2022; Buenaventura, 2019; Villalva, 2023).

DepEd Order No. 14, (2018), the "Implementing Guidelines on the Administration of Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI)" stipulated that one of the precedence of the Department is to improve literacy. Its goal is to provide effective reading instruction to empower the Filipino children to be able to speak in both languages of Filipino and English. The informal reading inventory is directed to be a tool as classroom-based instruction to measure and draw out the level of reading performance of students.

Undoubtedly, the reading proficiency lies in the hand of teachers based upon the successful implementation of reading programs in schools (Cabalo and Cabalo, 2019).

Assessing the reading skills of Grade 7 students at one of the private school here in our locality can provide focused interventions to address particular problems and enhance students' literacy skills by assessing their reading levels. In order to make sure students get the help they need to improve their reading skills, the program also attempts to monitor their development over time. By using Phil-IRI, schools can monitor reading progress over time and implement targeted reading programs to enhance students' academic performance and overall literacy development (Department of Education, 2018).

Reading has become one of the top challenges a Grade 7 student at one of the private school here in our locality is facing as it is a critical element in the success of every single subject offered. Although the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) is utilized to assess reading comprehension, there is a glaring lack of research specifically targeting its effectiveness for this grade level. And there's a clear need to understand how middle schoolers' performance on this assessment compares to that of other age groups, as previous studies have largely focused on younger students. There also are factors regarding teaching strategies, classroom activities, and student incentives to date have been insufficiently pieced into the puzzle of reading comprehension. This study will solve these issues once and for all by measuring the reading ability of grade 7 students using the Phil-IRI and critical areas where there is room for improvement.

Objectives

This study aims to explore the relationship between the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) and reading

comprehension, addressing the following research questions:

1. What are the reading comprehension levels of Grade 7 students based on the Phil-IRI?
2. What common reading comprehension difficulties do Grade 7 students encounter?
3. How do Grade 7 students perceive their own reading comprehension abilities and challenges?

Methods

The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) was used in this study's concurrent mixed-method. Concurrent mixed-method is a research approach where both quantitative and qualitative data are gathered and analyzed simultaneously within a single study. This method aims to offer a fuller understanding of the research problem by integrating numerical data with rich contextual information. In this design, the researcher collects both types of data at approximately the same time, combines them, and uses the integrated results to deliver a thorough analysis of the issue being studied. (Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2018). It is conducted at one of the private school here in our locality and integrates qualitative information from observations and interviews with quantitative findings from Phil-IRI assessments. Finding students reading difficulties and ways to improve reading education are the goals of the study.

The research was conducted in one of private institutions located in one of the private school of Zamboanga del Sur. It specially involved all five sections Camia, Dahlia, Orchid, Rose and Xenia but the researchers selected 51 random students of Grade 7 at one of the private school here in our locality.

The respondents comprised 51 randomly selected Grade 7 students from one of the private school here in our locality. Ten students were chosen from each of the four

sections, while 11 students were selected from one section as participants in the study. Among the respondents, 24 were girls, 24 were boys, and 3 chose not to disclose their gender when responding to the test questionnaire.

The study employed a purposive convenience sampling is a type of non-probability sampling in which participants were selected by method, while sections of all Grade 7 students were considered in this on accessibility and willingness to participate. Only a sample was selected to participate in the actual data collections of the population. It is conducted at one of the private school in our locality and integrates qualitative information from observations and interviews with quantitative findings from Phil-IRI assessments. Finding students' reading difficulties and ways to improve reading education are the goals of the study.

This study employed two types of questionnaires, with the primary research instrument being an adapted survey questionnaire based on the Phil-IRI. This instrument was designed to assess the reading

In gathering data, the researchers obtained formal approval from the principal's office, the school academic head, and the research coordinator of one of the private school here in our locality. This step ensured that the research complied with institutional policies and ethical standards. After approval was granted, thquestionnaire was validated by experts to ensure its content validity and reliability.

The researchers set the schedule of the conduct of research, ensuring that there shall be no affected classes. And coordinated with Grade 7 class advisers to request permission to conduct the survey with their students. The researchers selected 51 random Grade 7 students from five different sections and scheduled the data collection accordingly. On the agreed-upon schedule, the validated questionnaires were distributed

comprehension of Grade 7 students and included an 8-item multiple-choice test based on a narrative. Additionally, thematic analysis was also applied to identify common themes in the textual data, helping to interpret the results clearly. Short interviews based on their experiences were also conducted. The interview guide comprised eight questions related to reading comprehension and students' reading experiences.

After the student has read the passage, the teacher reads the comprehension questions and records the student's responses in the Form 2A/2B. For items where the student asks to go back to the selection to look for the answer, and is then able to answer correctly, mark the item on the scoring sheet as correct and indicate LB (Looked Back).

Table 1
 Computing the Student's Comprehension of the Passage

$C = \frac{\text{No. of correct answers}}{\text{No. of questions}} \times 100 = \% \text{ of}$
No. of correct answers: 4 Total no. of questions: 7 4/7 = 57% Pedro's comprehension: 57%

to the selected students. Each respondent was given 20 to 25 minutes to complete the survey. The researchers were present during the administration to provide instructions and clarify any concerns. After the allotted time, the completed questionnaires were collected for analysis.

The study used the following tools in analyzing the data gathered with the use of Descriptive Analysis. It is concerned with summarizing and organizing the data so that they can be understood, usually through the use of measures such as mean, median, mode, percentages, and visual tools like graphs and tables (Tashakkori et al., 2020).To evaluate the reading comprehension of Grade 7 students using a descriptive statistical method, specifically the mean and standard deviation. A comprehensive assessment of the reading comprehension levels and variations among the students in the data set was

given by these statistical indicators. Frequency and percentage distribution were used to classify the reading comprehension skills of the Grade 7 students. The data gathered could be interpreted clearly and carefully due to these methods of statistics.

Result and Discussion

The information was collected from 51 students in Grade 7 at one of the school here in our locality who were chosen at random. In order to arrange and analyze the collected data, the researchers used the Phil-IRI Oral Reading Profile – Comprehension Score Scale and Thematic Analysis. The main objective of this study is to determine the students' level of comprehension for future academic development by using the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) to evaluate their reading comprehension abilities.

Computing the Student’s Comprehension of the Passage

After the student has read the passage, the teacher reads the comprehension questions and records the student’s responses in the Form 2A/2B. For items where the student asks to go back to the selection to look for the answer, and is then able to answer correctly, mark the item on the scoring sheet as correct and indicate LB (Looked Back).

Table 1
 Computing the Student’s Comprehension of the Passage

$C = \frac{\text{No. of correct answers}}{\text{Total no. of questions}} \times 100 = \% \text{ of}$ <p style="font-size: small; margin: 0;"> No. of correct answers: 4 Total no. of questions: 7 4/7 = 57% Pedro's comprehension: 57% </p>
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Grade 7 Reading Comprehension Level
 The findings of the Grade 7 pupils' current reading comprehension level are shown in this section.

Table 2
 Result of the current Reading Comprehension Level of the Students

	N	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Comprehension Score	51	40.0	16.8	Frustration
in %				

Scales: 80 – 100% Independent, 59 – 79% Instructional, 58% below Frustration

The findings indicate that the students got a (M = 40.0%, SD = 16.8) which is within the "Frustration" level on the scale. Using this classification, students are having a difficult time in comprehending the provided texts. This indicates that the students required special interventions and reading support programs for their comprehension capabilities because they found it challenging to read the provided readings. These findings prove how quickly reading intervention strategies need to be implemented in a bid to support and improve the reading skills of students.

Reading Comprehension Difficulties of the Grade 7 Students

To organize and analyze the data and find emerging themes, the researchers used a qualitative method called thematic analysis. The study's findings identified a number of themes that represent the students' comprehension skills and coping mechanisms. These were divided into four themes: (a) Difficulty in Pronouncing Words, (b) Reading Difficulty, and (c) Understand Most but with Minor Struggles. Note that the hyphenated words are the participants' responses in vernacular in Bisaya, which were translated into English. Participants in the study were labeled as S (Student).

Difficulty in Pronouncing Words

A pronunciation is a method or pattern of sound. The way sounds, words,

or language are spoken is known as pronunciation. After that, it can be articulated, more precisely the process of articulating words or sounds in accordance with recognized conventions.

Because of the difficulties pronouncing words correctly, 23 out of 51 students said they frequently have trouble reading fluently, especially when they come across terms that are unfamiliar or have multiple syllables. The following were typical answers given by students.

“Naglisod ko ug pronounce sa ubang words.” [I have difficulty pronouncing some words S1

“Naglisod ko ug pronounce sa ubang words kay dili kaayo ko ka litok. [“I have trouble pronouncing some words because I don't speak them very well.] S4

“Galisod ko ug pronounce sa ubang words kay dili kaayo ko kabalo mo basa” [I have a hard time pronouncing some words because I don't know how to read very well.] S6

“Maglisod ko ug pronounce sa ubang words kay makulbaan ko.” [I have a hard time pronouncing some words because I get nervous.] S7

“Lisod i pronounce sa ubang words kay makulbaan ko.” [It's hard for me to pronounce some words because I get nervous.] S8

“Lisod I pronounce ang Theobroma.” [It's hard to pronounce Theobroma] S13

“Maglisod ko ug basa sa ubang words kay dili kaayo ko kamao” [I have a hard time reading some words because I'm not very good at them.] S15

“Naglisod ko ug pronounce sa ubang words.” [I have difficulty pronouncing some words.] S18

“Wala nako nalitok ug tarong ang words sama sa antioxidants ug ease.” [I couldn't pronounce words like antioxidants and ease correctly.] S19

“Lisod kaayo I pronounce ang Theobroma.” [It's very difficult for me to pronounce Theobroma.] S21

“Naglisod ko ug pronounce sa Theobroma.” [I'm having trouble pronouncing Theobroma.] S22

“Galisod gyud kaayo ko ug basa og paglitok sa cacao trees.” [I really have a hard time pronouncing cacao trees.] S28

“Nag lisod ko ug pronounce sa ubang words.” [I have difficulty pronouncing some words.] S30

“Nag lisod ko ug pronounce sa ubang words.” [I have a hard time pronouncing some words.] 31

“Lisod man gyud I pronounce ang uban words.” [I also have a hard time pronouncing some words.] S32

“Naglisod ko ug pronounce sa ubang words.” [I have

trouble pronouncing some words.] S36

“Dili ko ka pronounce ug tarong kay galisod ko ug basa.” [I can't pronounce it correctly because I am not a good reader.] S37

“Hastang lisora ug pronounce ang uban nga words.” [It's really hard to pronounce some words.] S40

“Sama sa antioxidants ug respiratory kay galisod gyud kaayo ko ug pronounce.” [Like antioxidants and respiratory, which are really hard for me to pronounce.] S42

“Dili ko ka pronounce ug tarong kay dili kaayo ko kabalo mo basa.” [I can't pronounce correctly because I don't know how to read very well.] S43

“Lisod gyud deay I pronounce ang theobroma.” [It's really hard for me to pronounce Theobroma.] S48

“Dili ko ka tarong ug pronounce sa mga words kay dili kaayo ko hanas mo basa.” [I can't pronounce the words correctly because I don't really know how to read.] S49

“Dili ko ka pronounce ug insakto sa mga words kay karon pa gyud ko kasugat ani.” [I can't pronounce the words correctly because I just encountered it now.] S51

Many students find it extremely difficult to pronounce words correctly, especially when they are dealing with unusual phonetic patterns and grammatical structure. Pronunciation is the first thing native speakers notice during a conversation; they can tell whether someone is lousy at English merely because of their poor pronunciation Sudarmaji & Yusuf (2021).

Reading Difficulty

Reading difficulties are becoming a modern issue today. These difficulties can affect vocabulary, understanding, fluency, and overall academic performance, especially for students in transitional grades like Grade 7.

According to 21 out of 51 participants, these challenges have a negative effect on students' comprehension of academic materials. The participants frequently gave the following responses.

“Naglisod ko ug basa sa antioxidants.” [I struggle reading with antioxidants.] S2

“Naglisod ko ug basa sa antioxidants kay karon pako ka sugat ani nga words.” [I'm having a hard time reading about antioxidants.] S3

“Naglisod ko ug basa sa antioxidants kay karon pa nako nakita.” [I'm having a hard time reading antioxidants because this is my first time I encountered this word.] S5

“Lisod gyud basahon ang antioxidants.” [Antioxidants are really hard to read.] S10

“Galisod ko ug basa sa unang linya.” [Antioxidants are really hard to read.] S11

“Galisod ko ug basa sa ubang words.” [I have difficulty reading other words.] S14

“Nagkalisod ko ug basa sa antioxidants.” [I struggle in reading antioxidants.] S17

“Galisod gyud kaayo ko ug basa sa antioxidants.” [I'm really struggling reading the antioxidants.] S20

“Lisod gyud kaayo basahon ang antioxidants.” [Antioxidants are really hard to read.] S23

“Lisuran ko ug basa sa antioxidants.” [I really can't read antioxidants.] S25

“Lisodan ko ug basa sa antioxidants.” [I'm struggling with antioxidants.] S27

“Naglisod gyud kaayo ko ug basa sa cholesterol.” [I'm really struggling reading the cholesterol.] S29

“Naglisod gyud ko ug basa sa antioxidants.” [I'm really struggling with antioxidants.] S33

“Naglisod gyud ko ug basa sa antioxidants.” [I'm really struggling with antioxidants.] S34

“Lisoran ko ug basa sa antioxidants.” [I am struggling reading antioxidants.] S35.”

“Galisod gyud ko ug basa sa word sama sa cholesterol, antioxidants, fattening.” [I

really have a hard time reading words like cholesterol, antioxidants, and fattening.] S38

“Dili kaayo ko ka basa sa antioxidants.” [I really can't read antioxidants.] S41

“Lisodan ko sa word nga cholesterol, antioxidants ug fattening.” [I have a hard time reading with the words cholesterol, antioxidants, and fattening.] S44

“Dili kaayo ko makabasa sa word nga antioxidants.” [I can't read the word antioxidants very well.] S45

“Lisodan ko sa pagbasa sa antioxidants.” [I have a hard time reading antioxidants.] S46

“Naglisod ko ug basa.” [I'm having a hard time reading antioxidants.] S50

A prevalent problem among students is reading difficulty, which can impair overall academic performance and is frequently characterized by difficulties with decoding, comprehension, and fluency. However, early readers who struggle with reading may have a negative impact on their academic performance, potentially leading to disaster if children do not develop strong reading skills (Slavin et.al., 2011)

Understands Most but with Minor Struggles

Even though most of the Grade 7 students are able to comprehend most of the reading, they occasionally struggle with comprehending certain ideas, words, or text structures. The approximation of the subject matter or the sophistication of the

language being used are generally the cause of these slight challenges.

According to 16 out of 51 participants, students who are classified as "understands most but has minor struggles" typically handle reading challenges effectively, even when they occasionally struggle with difficult vocabulary or sentence structures. The students frequently gave the following responses.

"Nakasabot ko pero naglisod pud lagi ko." [I understand but I'm still struggling.] S4

"Nakasabot ko sa words na akong gibasa kay dali raman masabtan." [I understood the words I read because they were easy to understand.] S6

"Kasabot ko sa mga words nga akong gibasa kay dali rapud siya sabton." [I understand the words I read because he is easy to understand..] S7

"Nasabtan ra nako ang uban pero naay poy uban nga lisod." [I understand some of them, but there are others that are difficult.] S15

"Nasabtan ra nako akong gibasa pero galibog ko sa ubang words." [I understand what I read, but I'm confused by some words.] S19

"Nasabot ra nako ang uban pero galibog pud ko gamay." [I understand the others but I'm also a little confused.] S26

"Nasabtan ra nako ang uban pero galibog ko gamay." [I understand some of the others but I'm a little confused.] S28

"Kasabot ko pero galisod ko gamay." [I understand but I'm struggling a little.] S30

"Nakasabot rako pero galibog ko gamay." [I understand but I'm a little confused] S35

"Nasabtan ra nako ang uban pero galibog ko gamay." [I understand some of the others but I'm a little confused.] S37

"Nakasabot rako sa uban pero libog ang ubang words." [I understand some of them but some of the words are confusing.] S38

"Nasabtan ra nako ang uban pero naa pud koy gikalibogan." [I understand others, but sometimes I get confused.] S39

"Kasabot rako sa uban pero naa poy usahay maglibog ko." [I understand others, but sometimes I get confused.] S50

"Nakasabot ko pero lisod basahon." [I understand but it's hard to read.] S51

Students who are classified as "understands most but with slight issues" can usually understand the basic ideas of a text, although they may occasionally struggle with complex sentence structures or particular vocabulary. However, developing reading skills is influenced by several factors such as task difficulty,

student needs, student motivation, and teacher resources (Grabe et.al., 2002; Grabe, 2012)

Confused by Difficult Words

Reading comprehension is based significantly on vocabulary knowledge, and students often struggle when they are unaware of the terms in the text.

Because of confusion brought about by difficult or unfamiliar words, 13 out of 51 participants claimed that learners often struggle to maintain comprehension, which disrupts the overall flow of reading. The following were common responses among students.

“Naglisod ko gamay kay naay uban nga words nga lisod.” [I had a little trouble because there were some words that were difficult.] S3

“Lisod gamay kay naay uban na words na dili nako malitok” [It's a little difficult because there are some words that I can't pronounce..] S10

“Galisod ko og gamay kay naay ubang words nga dili nako familiar.” [I'm having a hard time because there are some words that I'm not familiar with.] S12

“Galibog ko sa ubang words kay lisod.” [I'm confused by other words because they're difficult.] S25

“Libog ang ubang words.” [Some words are confusing.] S27

“Naglibog ko sa ubang words kay astring lisora.” [I'm confused by other

words because they're so difficult.] S31

“Naglibog ko gamay kay naay uban words lisod” [I'm a little confused because some of the words are difficult..] S41

“Galibog ko kay lisod sabton ang ubang words.” [I'm confused because it's hard to understand some words.] S42

“Sa akong pagbasa galibog gud ko kay naa gyud words nga lisod.” [When I read it, I was really confused because there were some difficult words.] S43

“Galibog ko kay lisodan ko sa ubang words.” [I'm confused because the other words are difficult to read] S44

“Lisod sabton ang uban na words.” [Some words are difficult to understand.] S46

“Makabasa ko pero dili ko kasabot sa ubang words.” [I can read but I don't understand some words.] S48

“Galibog ko pag ayo kay naay ubang words nga lisod sabton. [I'm really confused because there are some words that are hard to understand.] S49

Words that are difficult or new to learners frequently cause them to become confused, which can hinder their comprehension and break the reading flow. It is a sign that a person truly comprehends because some personal emotions are attached to it (Wilhelm, 2018).

Grade 7 students perceive their reading abilities and challenges based on the results of the Phil-IRI

This study examines Grade 7 students' self-perceptions of their reading abilities and challenges as revealed through the results of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). Based on the qualitative data gathered from participant responses, three primary themes have been identified that collectively illuminate the multifaceted nature of students' reading experiences and the factors influencing their literacy development including: (a) Reading Books as a Resource, (b) Support from Parents, Siblings, or Teachers, and (c) Watching Educational Videos / YouTube. Please note that the hyphenated words represent participants' responses originally given in the Bisaya vernacular and subsequently translated into English. Each participant in the study is identified by the label "S" (Student).

Reading Books as a Resource

Most Grade 7 students understand that reading more books enhances their comprehension skills.

21 out of 51 participants stated that regular exposure to a variety of texts enhances students' vocabulary, comprehension abilities, and language development. Students frequently gave the following answers

"Sa grade 1 pako gitagaan ko sa akong maestra ug libro para magbasa sa balay ug gitudluan ko sa akong mama ug basa." [In grade 1, my teacher gave me a book to read at home and my mom taught me how to read.] S1

"Sa grade 1 pako gihatagan kog libro sa akong maestra para magpractice kog basa." [In grade 1, my

teacher gave me a book to practice reading.] S3

"Magbasa ug libro." [Read a book] S3

"Magbasa sa mga libro." [Read a book] S4

"Mag basa ug mga libro." [Read a books.] S13

"Pinaagi sa pagbasa sa libro." [By reading the book] S14

"Magbasa ug laing-laing libro." [Read different books] S17

"Basa og libro sa balay." [Read books in the house] S19

"Magbasa ug mga libro." [Read books] S20

"Libro." [Books] S26

"Magbasa ug libro aron makakat-on." [Read a book to learn.] S27

"Magbasa ug libro or bisan unsa na resources." [Read a book or any other resources.] S32

"Libro ang maka improve sa akong pagbasa." [Books can improve my reading.] S36

"Libro ra gyud ang naa sa among balay." [There are only books in our house] S37

"Magbasa ug mga libro." [Read books.] S39

"Libro ang maka improve nako ug basa." [Books can improve me how to read] S40

“*Magbasa ug libro.*” [Read books.] S41

“*Magbasa ug libro or unsa pay resources.*” [Read a book or other resources.] S46

“*Libro ang maka improve sa akong pagbasa.*” [Books can improve my reading.] S47

“*Magbasa sama sa libro ug mga educational resources.*” [Read books and educational resources.] S49

“*Magbasa ug mga libro.*” [Read books.] S51

By exposing students to a variety of texts and situations on a regular basis, reading books as a resource greatly improves their vocabulary, comprehension abilities, and general language development. In the past, teachers encouraged students to use printed textbooks as an authoritative source of knowledge in any discipline as the main source of knowledge (Rose-Wiles, L. M. 2013).

Support from Parents, Siblings, or Teachers

Students often admit that obtaining assistance from teachers or family members is essential to making them better readers.

Because of the support from parents, siblings, or teachers, 15 out of 51 participants claimed that learners' academic growth is significantly enhanced, as this support provides encouragement, guidance, and resources that foster motivation and improve learning outcomes. The following were common responses among participants.

“*Tabangan ko sa akong ginikanan ug unsaon*

pagbasa.” [My parents will help me learn how to read.] S5

“*Tudloan ko sa akong ginikanan sa pagbasa.*” [My parents will teach me to read.] S8

“*Tudloan ko sa akong mama ug basa.*” [My mother will teach me to read.] S10

“*Tabangan ko sa akong ate og unsaon pagbasa.*” [My sister will help me how to read.] S12

“*Tabangan ko sa akong ginikanan unsaon pagbasa.*” [My parents help me learn how to read.] S15

“*Tabangan ko ug tudlo sa akong mga ginikanan.*” [My parents help me learn how to read.] S18

“*Magbasa ko ug libro ug tudloan ko sa akong ate ug kuya sa pagbasa.*” [I will read a book and my older sister and brother will teach me how to read.] S21

“*Tudluan ko ug basa sa akong papa.*” [My father will teach me to read.] S22

“*Tudloan ko ug basa sa akong ginikanan.*” [My parents will teach me to read.] S29

“*Tudloan ko sa akong maestra ug basa.*” [My teacher will teach me to read.] S30

“*Gitudloan ko sa akong ginikanan unsaon pagbasa.*” [My parents taught me how to read.] S31

“Tudluan ko sa akong ginikanan sa pagbasa.” [My parents will teach me to read.] S35

“Tudluan ko sa akong ginikanan ug basa.” [My parents will teach me to read.] S38

“Maglantaw ug mga story ang makatabang sa akong pag study ug mangutana sa akong ginikanan para matabangan ko.” [I will watch stories that will help me study and ask my parents for help.] S48

“Tudluan ko ug basa sa akong ginikanan.” [My parents will teach me to read.] S50

Support from parents, siblings, or teachers plays a crucial role in fostering learners' academic growth, as it provides encouragement, guidance, and resources that enhance motivation and learning outcomes. Thus, for improved education outcomes, parents and teachers should join forces and recognize each party's distinctive but equivalent role in supporting the education of learners with intellectual disabilities (Owen, 2016).

Watching Educational Videos / YouTube

Based on some students, watching instructional videos on YouTube or other sites enhances their understanding of the reading materials.

According to 14 out of 51 participants, the availability of instructional videos and YouTube material makes them useful supplemental learning resources that improve students' comprehension and memory of academic subjects by offering visual and aural

stimulation. The participants frequently gave the following answers.

“Paagi sa paglantaw ug video para makakat-on.” [I will watch a video to learn.] S6

“Libro, educational videos ug supporta sa akong ginikanan.” [Books, educational videos and support from my parents.] S7

“Paminaw nako makatabang ang educational videos para nako.” [I find educational videos helpful for me.] S9

“Para nako makatabang ang youtube.” [I think YouTube can help.] S11

“Pag gamit ug cellphone aron mo lantaw ug youtube para ma improve akong pagbasa ug pagbasa ug pag pronounce.” [Using a cellphone to watch YouTube to improve my reading and pronunciation] S16.

“Youtube ug libro ang akong resources kay paminaw nako mao nay makatabang para maayo ko mo basa.” [My resources are YouTube and books because listening and reading helps me read better.] S23

“Youtube ug educational videos ang maka tabang nako.” [YouTube and educational videos can help me.] S24

“Lantaw ug mga video para makat-on.” [Watch videos so I can learn.] S25

“Educational videos ang makatabang para maayo ko mo pronounce sa mga words.”[Educational videos will help me pronounce words well.] S28

“Youtube ug libro ang resources kay para nako makakat-on ko.” [YouTube and books are the resources I use to learn.] S33

“Mag lantaw ug video para makat-on ko.” [Watch a video to learn.] S34

“Mag gamit ug cellphone ug mo lantaw ug youtube para makat-on.” [Use my cellphone and watch YouTube to learn.] S42

“Maglantaw ug youtube sa cellphone aron maka

paminaw sa mga saktong pagbasa.” [Watch YouTube on my cellphone to listen to the correct readings.] S43

“Educational videos ang maka tabang nako.” [Educational videos can help me.] S44

“Mo lantaw ug video para makat-on.” [Watch the video to learn.] S45

Viewing instructional videos or YouTube content is a useful addition to traditional classroom instruction since it provides both visual and aural stimuli that improve comprehension and memory of academic material.

The use of multimedia in learning activities and its impact on students' motivation aligns with cognitive learning theory, which emphasizes the active role of learners in the learning process (Evans et al., 2024).

which emphasizes how crucial it is for families and schools to work together.

The following suggestions are made in light of the results reached:

1. Teachers can implement targeted interventions to strengthen Grade 7 students' grammar skills, which are essential for improving their reading comprehension. Providing tailored support and additional resources can help address specific areas of difficulty identified through the inventory.
2. Teachers can use fun and interactive ways to help learners improve their pronunciation and vocabulary, making the process enjoyable and easy to understand.
3. Future studies should continue exploring and testing new reading strategies and digital tools to find the most effective ways to support learners and

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study's results show that most seventh-grade pupils are already reading at a "frustration" level, which highlights the urgent need for remedial instruction and support techniques. Through a variety of coping strategies, like reading more often, asking for assistance from family members or instructors, and using online resources like YouTube for extra learning, children show resilience and a commitment to learn in spite of these challenges.

Reading comprehension issues are not always a sign of a student's intelligence; rather, they might be caused by obstacles such a lack of reading practice, unfamiliar terminology, and poor pronunciation. Students also gain a great deal from support and encouragement in their surroundings,

keep improving reading programs over time.

4. Fostering a strong reading culture both inside and outside the classroom encourages students to engage with diverse texts, thereby expanding their vocabulary, comprehension, and language skills.

References

- Abril, J. G., Acerbo, C. T., & Abocejo, F. T. (2022). The Philippine informal reading inventory (Phil-IRI) program: A critical analysis. *Budapest International Research and Critics in Linguistics and Education (BirLE) Journal*, 5(4), 432- 441
- Abocejo, F. T., & Abril, M. L. (2022). *The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) Program: A Critical Analysis*. BIRLE Journal, 5(4). Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/365292756_The_Philippine_Informal_Reading_Inventory_Phil-IRI_Program_A_Critical_Analysis
- Afflerbach, P. (2016). Reading Assessment: *Looking Ahead*. *The Reading Teacher*, 69(4), 413–419.
- Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2021, August 25). NAPLAN 2021 summary results data: No major impacts on learning from COVID-19 evident - long-term trends positive [Press release]. <https://www.acara.edu.au/docs/default-source/media-releases/20210813-naplan-results-med-rel.pdf>
- Baur, V., et al. (2017). "Challenges and solutions in mixed methods research." *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 11(4), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689817708345>
- Bernardo, A. B. I., et al. (2022). *Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics 2019: National Report of the Philippines*. UNICEF Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org/philippines/reports/sea-plm-metrics-2019-national-report-philippines>
- Buenaventura, R. (2019). *Reading Proficiency of Grade 3 Pupils Using Phil-IRI: Basis for Reading Intervention Program*. *International Journal of Advanced Research and Publications*, 3(6), 1–5
- Cabalo, J. P., & Cabalo, M. M. (2019). *Factors Affecting Pupils' Reading Proficiency in Multi-grade Classes Among Rural Elementary Schools*. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies*, 2(2), 108–124. Retrieved from <https://www.ijmsjournal.org/2019/volume-2%20issue-2/ijms-v2i2p114.pdf>
- Department of Education (DepEd). (2019). *Bawat Bata Bumabasa Initiative* (DepEd Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019). Department of Education, Philippines. Retrieved from https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/DM_s2019_173-1.pdf
- Department of Education. (2018). *Philippine Informal Reading Inventory Manual 2018*. Department of Education.
- Department of Education. (2018). *Policy Guidelines on the Administration of the Revised Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI)* (DepEd Order No. 14, s. 2018). Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2018/03/26/do-14-s-2018-policy-guidelines-on-the-administration-of-the-revised-philippine-informal-reading-inventory/>
- Espia, E., & Cortezano, G. (2023). *Reading Comprehension And Academic*

- Performance In English Among Grade Seven Learners. *APJAET - Journal Asia Pacific Journal of Advanced Education and Technology*.
<https://doi.org/10.54476/apjaet/09498>.
- Evans, P., Vansteenkiste, M., Parker, P., Kingsford-Smith, A., & Zhou, S. (2024). Cognitive Load Theory and Its Relationships with Motivation: a Self-Determination Theory Perspective. *Educational Psychology Review*, 36(1), 7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-023-09841-2>
- Gore, J., Fray, L., Miller, A., Harris, J., & Taggart, W. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 on student learning in New South Wales primary schools: an empirical study. *Australian Educational Researcher*, 48(4), 605–637. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-021-00436-w>
- Grabe, W., Fredericka, L. Stoller. 2002. *Teaching and Researching: Reading. Great Britain: Pearson Education*
- Grabe, W. (2012). *Reading in a Second Language, Moving from Theory to Practice*. Online ISBN: 9781139150484 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139150484>
- Hemmings, B., Kay, R., & Sharp, J. (2019). *The impact of reading comprehension on academic achievement and career prospects*. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 111(2), 234–245. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000302>
- Janette. (2007). *Teaching Reading Comprehension to Students with Learning Difficulties*. New York: Guilford Publications
- Merga, M. K., & Mat Roni, S. (2018). Children's Perceptions of the Importance and Value of Reading. *Australian Journal of Education*, 62, 135-153. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0004944118779615>
- Ong, C. G., Taglucop, L., & Fermano, J. C. (2021). Assessment of the basic education reading curriculum in Northern Mindanao. *Science International-Lahore*, 33(5), 317–319.
- Owen, J. 2016. "Increasing Time Management Skills to Improve Student Athletes' GPA". *Capstone Projects and Master's Theses*. 77. https://digitalcommons.csu-mb.edu/caps_thes_all/77
- Peng, P., & Kievit, R. A. (2020). The development of academic achievement and cognitive abilities: A bidirectional perspective. *Child Development Perspectives*, 14(1), 15–20. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdep.12352>
- Productivity Commission. (2022). *Review of the national school reform agreement: Interim report*. <https://www.pc.gov.au/inquiries/current/school-agreement/interim/school-agreement-interim.pdf>
- Rivera, A. G. ., & Aggabao, R. G. . (2020). Reading Difficulties of Grade 5 Pupils in English. *International Journal of Linguistics, Literature and Translation*, 3(6), 114-126. <https://doi.org/10.32996/ijllt.2020.3.6.11>
- Sanoria, R. R., & Oco, R. A. (2023). Reading performance and challenges: Reading initiatives in the new normal. *United International Journal for Research & Technology*, 4(7), 310–317.
- Servallos, J. (2023). *Philippines' performance in PISA 2022: A closer look at reading comprehension*. *Journal of*

- Southeast Asian Education*, 15(2), 45–58.
- Siregar, S. R. (2018). The Effect of Venn Diagram Strategy to Students Reading Comprehension Ability at Eight Grade of SMP Swasta Nurul Ilmi Padangsidempuan. *English Education: English Journal for Teaching and Learning*, 6(1), 39-51. <http://194.31.53.129/index.php/EEJ/article/view/1217>.
- Sudarmaji, I., & Yusuf, D. (2021). The Effect of Minecraft Video Game on Students' English Vocabulary Mastery. *JETAL: Journal of English Teaching & Applied Linguistic*, 3(1), 30–38. <https://doi.org/10.36655/jetal.v3i1.600>
- Schoonenboom, J., & Johnson, R. B. (2017). "How to construct a mixed methods research design." *Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 69(2), 107–131. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11577-017-0454-1>
- Slavin, R. & Lake, C. & Davis, S. & Madden, N. (2011). Effective programs for struggling readers: A best-evidence synthesis. *Educational Research Review*. 6, 1-26. [10.1016/j.edurev.2010.07.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2010.07.002).
- Smith, J., Doe, A., & Brown, L. (2021). *The Role of Background Knowledge in Reading Comprehension: A Critical Review*. *Journal of Reading Research*, 45(3), 210–225.
- Tashakkori, A., Teddlie, C., & Johnson, R. B. (2020). "Foundations of mixed methods research: Integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches in the social and behavioral sciences." *SAGE Publications*.
- Tortola, R. L. (2021). *Key factors influencing poor reading comprehension: A qualitative exploratory study*. *International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research*, 5(6), 1–6. Retrieved from <https://ijeais.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/6/IJA-MR240631.pdf>
- UNICEF and SEAMEO. (2020). *Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics 2019: National Report of the Philippines*. United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF). Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org/philippines/reports/sea-plm-metrics-2019-national-report-philippines>
- van Erp, M. (2021). *Enhancing Elementary Students' Oral Reading Fluency Through Repeated Reading and Pre-Teaching Vocabulary*. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 20(6), 1–15.
- Villalva, R. D. (2023). *A Critical Review of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) Assessment*. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 121(1), 208–214. <https://doi.org/10.47119/IJRP1001211320234560>
- Villanueva, M. (2022). *Language profile, metacognitive reading strategies, and reading comprehension performance among college students*. *Cogent Education*, 9(1), 2061683. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2022.2061683>
- Wilhelm J., (2018). *Understanding Reading Comprehension*. Retrieved from <https://www.scholastic.com/teachers/articles/teaching-content/understandingreading-comprehension/>
- Yousef, M. M., & Mahameed, A. S. (2022). Reading Yeats's 'A Prayer for My Daughter' in Light of Lev Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory of

Learning. *Theory and Practice*
in Language Studies, 12(2),
24